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Spatial structure of the herb layer of a pinewood community *Leucobryo-Pinetum* in Kraków-Częstochowa Upland (southern Poland)

Key words: pine forest, herb layer, spatial structure, numerical analysis, floristic diversity

Introduction

There are different ways of learning processes running inside plant communities. One of the commonest and weighting is the analysis of spatial structure. The basis of coactions and adaptations of plant species to each other and to habitat is main feature of the analysis and allows to differentiate the community into smaller fragments.

Mosaic structure could be detected by floristic analysis. It used to describe a phytocoenosis as the unit consisted of microcoenoses – units lower range (KWIATKOWSKA, 1972; BRZEZIECKI, 1987, 1988). Spatial analysis could be the useful way of studying anthropogenic changes of plant communities.

Present paper presents the attempt to analyse the horizontal microstructure of a pinewood community using numerical analysis of floristic composition.

Study area and methods

The investigations were carried out in the Kraków-Częstochowa Upland, near Jaroszwic Olkuski (Fig. 1). The pine forests are very typical communities for this region of Poland.

Phytosociologically they are described as *Leucobryo-Pinetum* association with transition features to *Peucedano-Pinetum* (WIKA, 1983).

The herb layer was analysed in 1994 using the permanent plot 8 x 62 m divided into 496 smaller adjacent squares 1 m² each (Greig-Smith's method) (GREIG-SMITH, 1967; KIMSA, 1991; KIMSA, BABCZYŃSKA-SENDEK, WIKA, 1992). On each quadrat the floristic composition was recorded together with percentage cover of the species occurring using the scale 1, 5, 10, 20, ..., 100%.

Floristic quantitative data were used to calculate the Shannon's index of diversity [H'] for each quadrat. The results were presented in the form of cartogram. The normal distribution of Shannon's index was confirmed by Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test. The same floristic data were used to perform numerical classification by Mulva-4 computer program (WILDI, ORLOCI, 1990) with following analysis options: square root transformation of cover values, covariance as a resemblance measure, complete clustering as classification method. As a result, there were distinguished 5 groups of quadrates called microcommunities. The characteristics of these groups were done.

Results

On the investigated plot there occur 36 vascular plant species (Table 1). Most important (with highest coverage and frequency) are *Deschampsia flexuosa*, species characteristic for the association, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Vaccinium myrtillus* – character species for the class and accompanying species – *Festuca ovina*.

The values of Shannon's index range from 0.14 to 0.63. The mean value of the index is 0.40 ± 0.09 . These values fitted quite well the normal distribution (Fig. 2) with most frequent class 0.40–0.45. Spatial distribution of the H' values is presented on the Fig. 3. The cartogram shows distinct groups of quadrates with higher and lower floristic diversity.

Cluster analysis revealed 5 microcommunities (types of quadrates) differentiating distinctly into 2 groups. Their relative similarity presents dendrogram (Fig. 4). The most frequent are the microcommunities 2 and 5 (Fig. 5). The spatial distribution of the microcommunities shows a few parts of the study plot where were particular types dominate (Fig. 6). Type 2 dominates in the lower part and the type 5 in the upper one. Table 2 presents the floristic composition of the distinguished microcommunities. The participation of the species is defined by multiplying frequency by mean cover.

Type 1 – *Deschampsia flexuosa-Vaccinium vitis-idaea* microcommunity is difficult to characterise. More frequent are *Pinus sylvestris* and especially *Diphysium complanatum*. In this only microcommunity occurs rare and protected species *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi*.

Type 2 – *Deschampsia flexuosa* microcommunity is characterised by very abundant presence of this grass. Here grow also *Lupinus polyphyllus* and *Hieracium pilosella*. Quite frequent is *Juniperus communis*.

Table 1

Floristic composition of the investigated plot

Group of species	a	b	c
Differentiating species of <i>Leucobryo-Pinetum</i> association			
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	360	10.2	1-80
Character species of <i>Dicrano-Pinion</i> alliance			
<i>Chimaphila umbellata</i>	158	0.5	1-5
<i>Pyrola chlorantha</i>	117	0.4	1-10
<i>Diphysium complanatum</i>	19	0.2	1-20
Character species of <i>Vaccinio-Piceetea</i> class			
<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	494	11.8	1-40
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	448	1.1	1-5
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	309	6.2	1-60
<i>Hieracium lachenalii</i>	154	0.6	1-10
<i>Orthilia secunda</i>	148	0.7	1-10
<i>Moneses uniflora</i>	65	0.3	1-10
Accompanying species			
<i>Festuca ovina</i>	470	13.1	1-70
<i>Melampyrum pratense</i>	307	1.3	1-10
<i>Luzula multiflora</i>	267	0.8	1-20
<i>Thymus serpyllum</i>	107	0.8	1-20
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	76	0.5	1-10
<i>Hieracium umbellatum</i>	67	0.2	1-10
<i>Chamaecytisus ratisbonensis</i>	40	1.4	1-90
<i>Salix caprea</i>	32	0.3	1-10
<i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i>	24	0.5	1-50
<i>Juniperus communis</i>	21	0.3	1-30
<i>Hypochoeris radicata</i>	14	0.2	1-40
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>	14	0.1	1-5
<i>Betula pendula</i>	12	0.1	1-5
<i>Agrostis tenuis</i>	12	0.1	1-5
<i>Populus tremula</i>	11	0.1	1-5
<i>Astragalus glycyphyllos</i>	10	0.5	1-70
<i>Salix arenaria</i>	6	0.1	1-5
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	5	0.03	1-5
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	4	0.03	1-10
<i>Solidago virgaurea</i>	3	0.03	5
<i>Rumex acetosella</i>	3	0.01	1
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	2	0.004	1
<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i>	2	0.004	1
<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i>	1	0.04	20
<i>Epilobium angustifolium</i>	1	0.01	5
<i>Padus avium</i>	1	0.002	1

Explanations: a - no of quadrats, b - mean cover in %, c - range of cover in %.

Fig. 1. A schematic map of the study area
 1 – investigated plot

Fig. 2. Histogram of Shannon's index values of the investigated plot

Fig. 3. Cartogram of the Shannon's index values spatial distribution on the investigated plot:
1 - 0.000-0.199, 2 - 0.200-0.399, 3 - 0.400-0.599, 4 - 0.600-0.799

Table 2

Floristic composition of the distinguished microcommunities

Species	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Festuca ovina</i>	1144.6	535.5	643.2	2170.0	1732.5
<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	1280.0	1390.0	590.0	1019.2	1070.0
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	1391.6	1989.4	79.2	296.0	44.0
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	55.8	1174.5	16.8	1070.0	12.8
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>				0.05	0.04
<i>Populus tremula</i>		0.2		0.1	1.6
<i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i>	3.8	17.1		0.3	0.01
<i>Solidago virgaurea</i>					0.2
<i>Padus avium</i>				0.01	
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	0.001	0.001			
<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i>	0.008				
<i>Epilobium angustifolium</i>		0.001			
<i>Rumex acetosella</i>				0.04	
<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i>					0.001
<i>Salix arenaria</i>	0.8	0.2			
<i>Astragalus glycyphyllos</i>	0.08				8.0
<i>Betula pendula</i>	0.09	0.3	0.6	0.18	0.01
<i>Juniperus communis</i>		7.2	0.18	0.6	
<i>Hypochoeris radicata</i>	1.0		0.18	0.02	1.0
<i>Agrostis tenuis</i>	0.5		0.6	0.02	0.24
<i>Salix caprea</i>	1.2	2.4	1.2	0.8	0.24
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	5.0	16.0	3.4	0.12	10.0
<i>Diphasium complanatum</i>	5.6	1.6		0.02	
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>			0.9		0.1
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>		0.4	0.09	0.01	
<i>Chamaecytisus ratibonensis</i>	1.4		2410.0		0.3
<i>Thymus serpyllum</i>	19.8	3.6	280.8	0.36	33.0
<i>Orthilia secunda</i>	12.0	17.0	66.3	25.6	10.5
<i>Hieracium umbellatum</i>	7.8		68.2		10.0
<i>Moneses uniflora</i>	3.2	0.6	38.5	0.14	12.6
<i>Pyrola chlorantha</i>	16.2	13.2	16.2	6.0	9.6
<i>Chimaphila umbellata</i>	10.8	13.2	10.2	21.0	9.6
<i>Melampyrum pratense</i>	99.4	74.2	180.6	81.2	76.8
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	114.0	108.0	63.2	79.2	100.1
<i>Luzula multiflora</i>	40.5	54.0	45.5	31.5	43.2
<i>Hieracium lachenalii</i>	29.7	29.7	8.1	10.8	15.0

Importance of species were given by product frequency and mean cover of the species

1 – *Deschampsia flexuosa-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*; 2 – *Deschampsia flexuosa*; 3 – *Chamaecytisus ratibonensis*; 4 – *Festuca ovina*; 5 – *Festuca ovina-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*.

Fig. 4. Dendrogram of the distinguished microcommunities of the investigated plot:

1 – *Deschampsia flexuosa-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*; 2 – *Deschampsia flexuosa*;
 3 – *Chamaecytisus ratisbonensis*; 4 – *Festuca ovina*; 5 – *Festuca ovina-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*

Fig. 5. Histogram of the distinguished microcommunities of the investigated plot:

1 – *Deschampsia flexuosa-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*; 2 – *Deschampsia flexuosa*; 3 – *Chamaecytisus ratisbonensis*; 4 – *Festuca ovina*; 5 – *Festuca ovina-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*

Fig. 6. Cartogram of the spatial distribution of the distinguished microcommunities on the investigated plot.

1 – *Deschampsia flexuosa-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*; 2 – *Deschampsia flexuosa*; 3 – *Chamaecytisus ratisbonensis*; 4 – *Festuca ovina*; 5 – *Festuca ovina-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*

Type 3 – *Chamaecytisus ratisbonensis* microcommunity is dominated by the species. Other plants, especially grasses are much less abundant. Some other species, such as *Thymus serpyllum*, *Orthilia secunda*, *Moneses uniflora*, *Hieracium umbellatum* and *Melampyrum pratense*, also characterise this group.

Type 4 – *Festuca ovina* microcommunity is mostly covered by this grass. Quite abundant is also *Vaccinium myrtillus*. *Chimaphila umbellata* occurs mainly in this group.

Finally, type 5 – *Festuca ovina-Vaccinium vitis-idaea* microcommunity is dominated by these two species. The specific feature of this type is low abundance of the *Vaccinium myrtillus*. Here grow clumps of *Astragalus glycyphyllos*.

Discussion

A part of the investigated plot was the subject of similar studies (KIMSÁ, 1991; KIMSÁ, BABCZYŃSKA-SENDEK, WIKÁ, 1992). Comparing the results it is to state that two species (*Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Pinus sylvestris*) are now more frequent, other species diminish their percentage cover. Also, we have not noticed 6 species recorded in 1991, but 4 new species are present.

In comparison to previous studies (KIMSÁ, BABCZYŃSKA-SENDEK, WIKÁ, 1992), we distinguished only 5 types of microcommunities as the sufficient level of differentiation. KWIATKOWSKÁ, SYMONIDES (1985) calculated the Shannon's diversity index for pine forest community as 0.55. For present plot the mean value is 0.40. But the basis for measure in above-mentioned paper was biomass of particular plant populations and in our study – the percentage cover. This method is the only possible for permanent plot studies.

Table 3

The post – hoc comparisons of Shannon's index means by Tukey test for unequal N ($p < 0,01$). There are no significant differences between studied microcoenosis

Microcoenosis	Means	Value of Tukey test			
1	0.42170				
2	0.40254	0.72192			
3	0.45493	0.62376	0.17354		
4	0.39403	0.37041	0.96574	0.07474	
5	0.38863	0.19604	0.67570	0.04034	0.99377

Explanations: 1 – *Deschampsia flexuosa-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*; 2 – *Deschampsia flexuosa*; 3 – *Chamaecytisus ratisbonensis*; 4 – *Festuca ovina*; 5 – *Festuca ovina-Vaccinium vitis-idaea*.

The cartograms both of microcommunities and floristic diversity show some degree of heterogeneity of the investigated phytocoenosis occur. Nevertheless, there are areas on the plot with high degree of homogeneity. Comparison of these two cartograms shows also that there are no distinct relations between diversity and composition. The post – hoc comparisons of means by Tukey test for unequal samples (Tab. 3) confirmed this statement. There are no significant differences between studied microcoenosis.

Conclusions

Investigated pinewood phytocoenosis could be described as relatively heterogeneous with regard to floristic composition and diversity. Numerical classification method is highly recommended for studies of spatial structure of the herb layer. It enables detailed analysis of this structure. Present studies show also that both floristic composition and floristic diversity could be used as highly independent indices of spatial structure.

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STRUKTURA PRZESTRZENNA RUNA
BORU SOSNOWEGO *LEUCOBRYO-PINETUM*
NA WYŻYNIIE KRAKOWSKO-CZĘSTOCHOWSKIEJ (POŁUDNIOWA POLSKA)

Streszczenie

Poziomą strukturę warstwy runa w borze sosnowym analizowano za pomocą współczynnika różnorodności florystycznej Shannona oraz klasyfikacji numerycznej, stosując pakiet Mulva-4. Badania prowadzono na stałym poletku podzielonym na 496 kwadratów o wielkości 1 m². Podstawą analizy ilościowej było procentowe pokrycie roślin naczyniowych runa. Wartość współczynnika Shannona wahała się w granicach 0,14–0,63. Wyróżniono 5 grup kwadratów (nazwanych mikrozbiorowiskami) i scharakteryzowano je florystycznie. Stwierdzono, że warstwa runa badanego boru sosnowego wykazuje pewną heterogenność. Autorzy konkludują, że zastosowane metody analizy ilościowo-florystycznej wyjawiają nawet drobne różnice w strukturze przestrzennej fitocenzoz.

ПРОСТРАНСТВЕННАЯ СТРУКТУРА ТРАВЯННОГО ПОКРОВА
СОСНОВОГО БОРА *LEUCOBRYO-PINETUM*
НА КРАКОВСКО-ЧЕНСТОХОВСКОЙ ВОЗВЫШЕННОСТИ (ЮЖНАЯ ПОЛЬША)

Резюме

Горизонтальную структуру яруса травянного покрова в сосновом бору проанализировано, используя показатель флористического разнообразия Шанона и нумеричную классификацию при помощи программы Mulva-4. Исследования произведены на постоянной площади опробования, разделенной на 496 квадратов площадью 1 м². Основой количественного анализа было процентная проекция сосудистых растений в покрове. Значение показателя Шанона колебалось в границах 0,14–0,63. Выделено 5 групп квадратов (названных микро-сообществами) и дана их флористическая характеристика. Установлено, что ярус травянного покрова исследованного соснового бора проявляет определенную гетерогенность. Авторы пришли к выводу, что применение метода количественно-флористического анализа выявляет даже небольшие различия в пространственной структуре фитоценозов.

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